

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ
JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ДАВРИЙЛИГИ: 2016-2026

ЖИЛД 11
СОҢ 2

2026

ЧОП
ЭТИЛГАН САНА:
20.04.2026

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

11 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 11, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 11, ISSUE 2

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Ўзбекистон Республикаси
Фанлар академиясининг Иммунология ва инсон
геномикаси институти директор ўринбосари,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна
Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги

Jin Young Choi
Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти

Kemalettin Aydin
профессор Sağlık Bilimleri Üniversitesi ректори, **ORCID**
ID: 0000-0003-0714-7075

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Оринов Фирдавс Суръатович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович
тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент давлат тиббиёт
университети Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очиллов Улдуғбек Усмонович
DSc, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиева
DSc, Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович
Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхисси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор, Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Алимов Жалолiddин Усмон ўғли
PhD, Доцент Тошкент Давлат тиббиёт университети
Чирчиқ филиали, **ORCID ID:** 0009-0009-3959-9878

Саидов Садаммир Абборович
тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабалджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент давлат тиббиёт
университети, Тери-таносил, болалар тери-таносил
касаликлари ва ОИТС кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент давлат тиббиёт
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайберганиевна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси профессори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
2-сон Даволаш факултети декани,
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент.
Самарқанд, Ўзбекистон.

Миржурев Элбек Миршавкатович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
ЎзССР Тиббий ходимларни касбий малакасини
ривожлантириши марказининг Нејрорехабилитация
кафедраси мудири, Тошкент, Ўзбекистон

Тағоев Шерқабул Бойқабулович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, хирургия кафедраси
доценти Тошкент давлат тиббиёт университети.
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.

Сайфутдинов Зайниддин Асамутдинович
PHD, Республика ихтисослаштирилган педиатрия илмий-
амалий тиббиёт маркази, **ORCID ID:** 0009-0007-5270-1297

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, Заместитель директора Института иммунологии и геномики человека Академии наук Республики Узбекистан, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна
директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi
профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Kemalettin Aydin
профессор, ректор Университета медицинских наук (Sağlık Bilimleri Üniversitesi), ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0714-7075

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна
Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улдулбек Усманович
DSc, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна
DSc, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович
Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор Душанбе, Таджикистан <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Алимов Жалолиддин Усмои угли
PhD, Доцент Чирчикского филиала Ташкентского Государственного медицинского университета, ORCID ID: 0009-0009-3959-9878

Саидов Садаммир Аброрович
доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович
доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет, доцент кафедры Дерматовенерология, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич
Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Мирджараев Эльбек Миршавкатович
Заведующий кафедрой Нейрореабилитации Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников МЗ РУз, д.м.н., профессор Ташкент, Узбекистан

Тагаев Шеркабул Бойкабулович
доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры хирургии, Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет. ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.

Сайфутдинов Зайниддин Асамутдинович
PHD, Республиканский специализированный научно-практический медицинский центр педиатрии ORCID ID: 0009-0007-5270-1297

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Deputy Director of the Institute
of Immunology and Human Genomics of the Academy of
Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD, Docent Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Kemalettin Aydin

*Professor, Rector of Health Sciences University (Sağlık Bilimleri
Universitesi), ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0714-7075*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent State
Medical University. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*DSc, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Alimov Jaloliddin Usmon Ugli

*PhD, Associate Professor at Chirchik Branch of Tashkent State
Medical University, ORCID ID: 0009-0009-3959-9878*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent State
Medical University, Docent the Department of
Dermatovenerology, pediatric dermatovenerology
and AIDS, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganova

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich

*Dean of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2, Samarkand State
Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate
Professor. Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Mirjuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich

*Head of the Department of Neurorehabilitation Center
for the development of professional qualification of
medical workers, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2111-4388>*

Tagaev Sher Kabul Baykabulovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
of Surgery Department, Tashkent State Medical University
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

Sayfutdinov Zayniddin Asamutdinovich

*PHD, Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical
Center of Pediatrics ORCID ID: 0009-0007-5270-1297*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Negmadjanov Bakhodur Boltayevich, Makhmudova Sevara Erkinovna.**
ETIOLOGY AND MOLECULAR GENETIC IDENTIFICATION OF CONGENITAL FEMALE GENITAL TRACT ANOMALIES.....12
2. **Agababyan Larisa Rubenovna, Usmankulova Khabiba Mizrobjonovna.**
ASSISTED REPRODUCTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TREATMENT OF INFERTILITY IN WOMEN WITH PCOS.....23

ANESTHESIOLOGY AND INTENSIVE CARE MEDICINE

3. **Pardaev Shukur Kuylievich, Sharipov Isroil Latipovich.**
MODERN APPROACHES TO ENSURING RESPIRATORY TRACT CONDUCTIVITY DURING MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY IN CHILDREN.....31

HAEMATOLOGY

4. **Lipartia Mary Givievna, Mutalova Zumrad Sanzhar kizi.**
PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF HEMOLYTIC ANEMIAS: A NARRATIVE REVIEW.....36
5. **Abdurakhmanova N. R., Kayumov A. A.**
PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF CD123 (IL3RA) EXPRESSION IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE LEUKEMIAS.....45

PEDIATRIC SURGERY

6. **Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich, Sultanov Temur Ismailovich.**
CURRENT ISSUES IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF THE RECTAL ULTRA-SHORT SEGMENT FORM OF HIRSCHSPRUNG'S DISEASE IN CHILDREN (LITERATURE REVIEW).....52
7. **Kholmetov Shukhrat Shamkhatovich, Khotamov Khusnitdin Narzullaevich.**
SURGICAL METHODS FOR THE CORRECTION OF RENAL FUNCTION DISORDERS IN CHILDREN.....61

PUBLIC HEALTH AND HEALTH CARE SYSTEM

8. **Mamedova Guzalya Bakirovna, Madiyarova Farina Umidovna.**
OPTIMIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL CYCLE IN AN INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC HUB: ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL BASED ON MICROSOFT PROJECT.....68
9. **Utepv Parkhat Dusembaevich, Rizaev Zhasur Alimdzhonovich, Tukhtarov Bakhrom Eshnazarovich.**
A SYSTEM FOR TRAINING SPECIALISTS IN BIOLOGICAL SAFETY AND BIOLOGICAL PROTECTION IN MEDICAL ORGANIZATIONS.....72

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

10. **Seyfullaeva Bagdagul Skenderbekovna, Abduxalilova Gulnora Kudratullaevna.**
DETERMINATION OF STABILITY CHARACTERISTICS OF PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA STRAINS USED IN AN EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT PANEL.....81

11. **Nabieva Dilnoza Djurayevna.**
CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF DERMATOLOGICAL DISEASES IN CHILDREN WITH HIV INFECTION.....94
12. **Oslanov Absamat Abdurakhimovich, Fayzullaev Sherzod Kobiljon ugli, Shakharov Dilshod Jura ugli, Tukhtaev Shokhzod Eshmurod ugli.**
CASES OF DRUG-INDUCED LIVER DAMAGE IN THE FIBROUS STAGE OF CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS “B”.....99
13. **Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna.**
DIAGNOSIS OF BACTERIAL COMPLICATIONS IN COVID-19-ASSOCIATED PNEUMONIA.....108
14. **Samibaeva Umida Khurshidovna.**
ETIOPATHOGENETIC ASPECTS OF THE NEW CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19 (LITERATURE REVIEW)116
15. **Shadjalilova Mukarram Salimdjanovna, Xalilova Zuhra Telmanovna.**
MODERN DYNAMICS OF SPREAD AND CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF BACTERIAL INFECTIONS OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT.....125

DERMATOLOGY AND VENEREOLOGY

16. **Tashkenbaeva Umida Alisherovna, Abboskhonova Fotima Khasanovna.**
THE ROLE OF GENETIC AND BEHAVIORAL FACTORS IN FORMING THE SEVERITY OF ALOPECIA IN POSTBARIATRIC PATIENTS130
17. **Tashkenbaeva Umida Alisherovna, Abboskhonova Fotima Khasanovna.**
THE INFLUENCE OF CONCOMITANT DISEASES AND INDIVIDUAL FACTORS ON THE DEGREE OF ALOPECIA IN PATIENTS AFTER BARIATRIC INTERVENTIONS.....135

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

18. **Gasymov Ayaz Veli oglu, Panahiyan Vafa Mustafa oglu, Abilova Farida Arif kyzy, Khatamov Jakhongir Abruevich.**
CONGENITAL CHOLESTEATOMA IN ADULTS.....140
19. **Khatamov Jakhongir Abruevich.**
OUR EXPERIENCE IN THE TREATMENT OF ALLERGIC RHINITIS.....146

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDIES

20. **Khamidova Farida Muinovna, Nojhigitov Azamat Musakulovich.**
THE INFLUENCE OF GSTM1 GENETIC POLYMORPHISM ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRONCHIECTASIS.....151
21. **Khamzaev Komiljon Amirovich, Farangiz Bahrom kizi Mamatkulova, Akhmatalieva Mayram.**
MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF KIDNEY DAMAGE IN CHILDREN WITH IGA NEPHROPATHY.....163

ONCOLOGY AND RADIATION MEDICINE

22. **Tillyashaikhov Mirzagolib Nigmatovich, Khakkulov Erkin Bekmirzayevich, Alimov Jaloliddin Usmonkhon ugli.**
ANALYSIS OF URODYNAMIC PARAMETERS IN THE ASSESSMENT OF OVERACTIVE BLADDER IN PATIENTS WITH PROSTATE CANCER.....173

23. **Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatona, Khoshimov Bakhodir Bakhromovich.**
MYOSTEATOSIS IN METASTATIC GYNECOLOGIC CANCER: CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM.....184
24. **Yusupbekov Abrorbek Ahmedjanovich, Tuychiyeva Sabokhat Shavkatovna, Djanklich Saide Mustafayevna.**
A POPULATION-BASED APPROACH TO CERVICAL CANCER: THE CONTEMPORARY IMPORTANCE OF CANCER REGISTRIES, SCREENING, AND SURVIVAL ANALYSIS.....191
25. **Ulmasov Firdavs Gayratovich, Yarmukhamedova Nargiza Anvarovna, Raufov Farkhod Makhmudovich.**
MODERN TREATMENT METHODS OF BREAST CANCER (LITERATURE REVIEW).....199
26. **Karimova Nargiza Sunnatillayevna, Xasanboyev Saidjon G'ayratjon o'g'li.**
OPTIMIZATION OF RADIOTHERAPY PLANNING FOR HEAD AND NECK TUMORS BASED ON THE INTEGRATION OF MULTIPARAMETRIC IMAGING DATA.....206
27. **Zaredinov Damir Arifovich, Li Marina Vladimirovna, Goziev Soyibjon Orivjonovich.**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF RADIATION EXPOSURE TO THE SKIN OF THE HANDS OF NUCLEAR MEDICAL PERSONNEL.....218
28. **Minnulin Irkin Rashidovich, Rakhimberdiev Rustam Abdunasirovich, Mirzakulov Buned Gaybullaevich, Tursunov Sherali Sirozhiddinovich, Urazov Nuriddin Elmurotovich**
UNRESOLVED ISSUES OF MEDICATION RELATED OSTEONECROSIS OF THE JAW IN BIPHOSPHONATE TREATMENT OF BONE METASTASES FROM PROSTATE CANCER.....224

OPHTHALMOLOGY

29. **Kadirova Aziza Muratovna.**
COMPLEX THERAPY OF RETROBULBAR NEURITIS OF VIRAL ORIGIN.....232
30. **Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Abdullaeva Zulfiya Bakhodirovna.**
CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VISUAL FUNCTIONS IN CHILDREN WITH PARTIAL ATROPHY OF THE VISUAL NERVE.....237
31. **Turakulova Dilfuza Mukhitdinovna, Nazirova Zulfiya Rustamovna, Karabayeva Iroda Murodjonovna.**
FEATURES OF CARRYING OUT CHILDREN WITH PRIMARY CONGENITAL GLAUCOMA ASSOCIATED WITH STERGE-WEBER SYNDROME.....242

PEDIATRIC DISEASES

32. **Makhmudova Ezoza Oybek kizi. Usmanova Munira Fayzullaevna Kardjavova Gulnoza Abilkasimovna.**
CURRENT DIRECTIONS IN RESPIRATORY THERAPY IN PRETERM INFANTS: PATHOGENESIS MECHANISMS, COMPLICATION PREVENTION MEASURES, AND EVALUATION OF THERAPEUTIC EFFECTIVENESS.....249
33. **Abdullaeva Durдона Rustamovna.**
DIGITAL VISUAL LOAD, ACCOMMODATIVE DISORDERS, AND COGNITIVE FATIGUE IN SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN.....265
34. **Akhmedzhanova Nargiza Ismailovna.**
ASSESSMENT OF IRON LEVELS DEPENDING ON THE TYPE OF ANEMIA IN CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE IN CHILDREN.....273

35. **Fayzakhmatova Feruza Ozod kizi, Khamzaev Komiljon Amirovich, Mamatkulov Bahrom Bosimovich.**
USING MONOCLONAL ANTIBODIES IN THE TREATMENT OF STEROID-SENSITIVE NEPHROTIC SYNDROME IN CHILDREN.....281
36. **Khalilov Mirziyod Kholmurot ugli, Khamzaev Komiljon Amirovich, Akhmatalieva Mayram.**
GENETIC BASIS OF STEROID-RESISTANT NEPHROTIC SYNDROME IN CHILDREN AND ITS CLINICAL CORRELATIONS.....290
37. **Khamzaev Komiljon Amirovich, Bondarenko Anastasiya Romanovna, Akhmatalieva Mayram.**
EFFECT OF IMMUNOSUPPRESSIVE REGIMENS ON THE RELAPSE RATE AND CUMULATIVE CORTICOSTEROID DOSE IN CHILDREN WITH FREQUENTLY RECURRENT NEPHROTIC SYNDROME.....301

PSYCHIATRY AND NEUROLOGY

38. **Ravshanov Jakhongir, Ashurov Zarifjon.**
THE IMPACT OF SYNTHETIC CATHINONES ON SUICIDAL BEHAVIOR: A RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DEPENDENCE.....310
39. **Rakhmatullaeva Gulnora Kutpiddinova, Maksudova Odina Arabbaevna.**
DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF PHENOTYPIC SIGNS AND THE BEIGHTON AND VAS SCALES IN IDENTIFYING UNDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA IN DORSOPATHY.....317
40. **Kuchimova Charos Azamatovna, Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich.**
CLINICAL AND DYNAMIC ASSESSMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY AND QUALITY OF LIFE INDICATORS IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH DEPRESSIVE CONDITIONS ASSOCIATED WITH PSYCHOORGANIC SYNDROME.....326
41. **Ashurov Zarifjon, Abdulkakharova Gulnoza.**
THE GROWING CHALLENGE OF SYNTHETIC CATHINONES AND PRESCRIPTION DRUG MISUSE IN UZBEKISTAN.....333

MEDICAL REHABILITATION

42. **Kobilov Azizjon Orzikulovich, Saidov Sokhib Saidmurodovich, Yusupov Shukhrat Abdurasulovich.**
COMPLEX REHABILITATION EXPERIENCE OF CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF LUMBAR DISC HERNIATION.....340
43. **Isakova Gulchekhra Saitalieva**
EFFICACY OF THE MONTESSORI METHOD IN COMPLEX REHABILITATION OF SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY.....346

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

44. **Khaydarov Artur Mikhaylovich, Rakhimov Akbarbek Rasulbek ugli.**
ETIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS FOLLOWING DENTAL IMPLANTATION.....351
45. **Islamova Nilufar Bustanovna, Nurullayeva Guzal Abdumalikovna.**
IMPROVEMENT OF ADHESIVE TECHNOLOGIES APPLICATION FOR THE PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS AFTER TOOTH BLEACHING.....355
46. **Akhmedov Alisher Astanovich, Toyirov Jahongir Sobirovich.**
MODERN CONCEPTS OF TREATMENT IN ACCELERATED TOOTH TISSUE DESTRUCTION.....362

47. **Ortikova Nargiza Khayrullayevna, Khurramova Surayyo Dustmurodovna.**
OPTIMIZATION OF ORTHOPEDIC DENTAL TREATMENT METHODS IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.....369
48. **Durdiyeva Umida Berdimuradovna, Fattakhov Ravshan Abdurashidovich.**
CURRENT STATE OF THE PROBLEM OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH SOMATIC PATHOLOGY (RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS): PATHOGENETIC RELATIONSHIPS AND CLINICAL APPROACHES.....376
49. **Vohidov Elbek Rahimovich, Rizaev Jasur Alimdjanovich.**
DENTAL HEALTH ASSESSMENT INDICATORS FOR MECHANICAL ENGINEERING WORKERS.....384
50. **Islamova Nilufar Bustanovna, Nabiyeva Marjona Uktamovna.**
IMPROVING THE METHODS OF TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS DURING THE ADAPTATION PERIOD OF PATIENTS TO REMOVABLE DENTURES.....390
51. **Norqulov Muslim Muhiddin ugli.**
MODERN STRATEGIES AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN COMPREHENSIVE REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH MANDIBULAR FRACTURES.....400
52. **Norqulov Muslim Muhiddin ugli.**
RISK FACTORS ANALYSIS AND MODERN APPROACHES TO THE PREVENTION OF INFECTIOUS COMPLICATIONS IN MANDIBULAR FRACTURES.....406
53. **Hayitova Mehriqul Alijon kizi, Rajabov Otabek Asrorovich.**
ERYTHEMA MULTIFORME EXUDATIVE IN THE ORAL CAVITY.....413
54. **Pulatov Oybek Abdumutolovich**
EFFICACY OF (GANOZHI PLUS) APPLICATION IN ADOLESCENTS FOLLOWING ORTHODONTIC BRACKET SYSTEM TREATMENT.....421
55. **Ismailov Saydimurad Ibragimovich, Zufarov Mirjamol Mirumarovich, Sharapov Nodir Utkirovich, Alieva Salima Bobosafarovna, Abdullaeva Mokhima Abdullaevna, Mirzaev Xondamir Alisher ugli.**
CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF WOMEN WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE IN THE SELECTION OF MYOCARDIAL REVASCULARIZATION METHODS.....425

PHARMACOLOGY

56. **Miskinova Fazilat Khudayorovna.**
STUDY OF THE ANALGESIC ACTIVITY OF N-BENZYL CYTISINE DERIVATIVES AND 1-PHENYLISOQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES.....438
57. **Abdurasulova Nargiza Olimovna, Ergashova Madina Muxtorovna.**
HYPOTENSIVE AND ORGANOPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES OF TELMISARTAN, A MEMBER OF THE SARTAN GROUP OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS.....443

INTERNAL MEDICINE

58. **Agababyan Irina Rubenovna, Rustamova Sarvinoz Botir kizi.**
THE IMPORTANCE OF EPICARDIAL ADIPOSE TISSUE IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES (LITERATURE REVIEW).....448
59. **Fattakhov Rafkat Akramovich**
METABOLIC DISORDERS AND THE RISK OF MULTIMORBIDITY IN PATIENTS WITH COPD.....455

60. **Fattakhova Yulia Edgarovna**
 THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VITAMIN D LEVELS AND ANXIETY-DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS AND THE SEVERITY OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE.....466

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

61. **Irismetov Murod Ergashevich, Khoshimov Javlon Tavakkalovich.**
 POSTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT INJURY OF THE KNEE JOINT DIAGNOSIS AND ARTHROSCOPIC SURGERY.....476

UROLOGY

62. **Gafarov Rushen Refatovich, Shookla Pooja, Mansurov Umar Makhmudovich.**
 THE ROLE OF TRIBULUS TERRESTRIAL PREPARATIONS IN THE TREATMENT OF SEXUAL DISORDERS IN MEN.....484

SURGERY

63. **Togayev Sherkobul Baykobulovich, Norboyev Olim Ibodullayevich, Hasanov Bobur Abduganievich.**
 TOTAL COLECTOMY FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF CROHN'S DISEASE OF THE COLON.....497

64. **Amonov Xudoyberdi Ravshanovich.**
 SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CHRONIC COLOSTASIS: RISK FACTORS FOR UNFAVORABLE OUTCOMES AND STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE POSTOPERATIVE QUALITY OF LIFE.....501

65. **Ruziboev Sanjar Abdusalomovich, Amonov Xudoyberdi Ravshanovich.**
 OPTIMIZATION OF THE SELECTION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT METHODS FOR CHRONIC COLOSTASIS BASED ON COMPREHENSIVE CLINICAL AND FUNCTIONAL ASSESSMENT.....519

ENDOCRINOLOGY

66. **Mamadiyarova Dilshoda Umirzokovna.**
 THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE C47T (RS4880) POLYMORPHISM IN THE SOD2 GENE IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND PERIOD OF COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETES.....529

67. **TOGAYEV Sherkobul Baykobulovich**
 FOURNIER GANGRENE (CASE REPORT).....534

68. **Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна, Махкамов Акбаржон Мурод угли**
 РОЛЬ ЭТИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ФАКТОРА В ВЫБОРЕ ТАКТИКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО РИНОСИНСИТА У ДЕТЕЙ.....538

69. **UMAROVA Nazifa Abduraufovna, SATVALDIEVA Elmira Abusamatovna, SALIKHOVA Kamola Shavkatovna**
 CURRENT CONCEPTS OF NECROTIZING ENTEROCOLITIS IN NEWBORNS: PATHOGENESIS, DIAGNOSIS AND NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT.....541

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

UDC 616.89-008.441.13:615.214

ASHUROV ZarifjonDepartment of Psychiatry and Narcology
Tashkent State Medical University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan**ABDUKAKHAROVA Gulnoza**Department of Psychiatry and Narcology
Tashkent State Medical University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

THE GROWING CHALLENGE OF SYNTHETIC CATHINONES AND PRESCRIPTION DRUG MISUSE IN UZBEKISTAN

For citation: Ashurov Zarifjon, Abdukakharova Gulnoza. The Growing Challenge of Synthetic Cathinones and Prescription Drug Misuse in Uzbekistan // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2026, vol. 11, issue 2.

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19815506>

ABSTRACT

The increasing prevalence of synthetic narcotic substances and psychoactive pharmaceutical drug use has become a significant public health concern. This study analyzes trends in substance use in Uzbekistan from 2022 to 2024, focusing on demographic patterns, shifts in drug preferences, and the rising misuse of prescription medications. **Methods.** A retrospective observational cohort study was conducted using official national registries and medical statistical reports. The study included all registered users of synthetic cathinones, anticonvulsants, and other psychoactive substances during the three-year period. Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were applied, including trend analysis, chi-square tests, correlation analysis, and logistic regression modeling, to assess patterns of substance use by age, gender, and drug type. **Results.** The total number of registered users nearly doubled between 2022 (409 cases) and 2024 (933 cases), highlighting a sharp rise in synthetic drug use. Males accounted for approximately 89–90% of all cases, while the number of female users increased from 41 in 2022 to 102 in 2024. The 18–34 age group represented the highest-risk demographic, with nearly 70% of all cases. Among synthetic cathinones, α -PVP replaced mephedrone as the most commonly used stimulant, with cases rising from 36 in 2022 to 319 in 2024. Pregabalin misuse also increased, becoming the most frequently abused anticonvulsant (274 cases in 2024). While tropicamide use remained relatively stable (25–30 cases annually), its share in the overall structure declined. **Conclusions.** The findings indicate a rapid transformation in substance use patterns in Uzbekistan, with synthetic cathinones and prescription drugs gaining popularity. The dominance of α -PVP and the increased misuse of pregabalin underscore the need for stricter pharmaceutical regulation, targeted prevention strategies, and expanded access to treatment programs. Addressing these trends requires a comprehensive public health response.

Key words: synthetic cathinones, α -PVP, mephedrone, pregabalin, substance use trends, Uzbekistan, public health, prescription drug misuse, epidemiological analysis, addiction.

ASHUROV ZarifjonPsixiatriya va narkologiya kafedrası
Toshkent davlat tibbiyot universiteti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston**ABDUKAKHAROVA Gulnoza**Psixiatriya va narkologiya kafedrası
Toshkent davlat tibbiyot universiteti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston**O'ZBEKISTONDA SINTETIK KATINONLAR VA RETSEPT BO'YICHA BERILADIGAN DORI VOSITALARINI SUISTE'MOL QILISH MUAMMOSINING KUCHAYIB BORISHI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Sintetik narkotik moddalar va psixoaktiv dori vositalarini iste'mol qilishning ortib borishi jamoat salomatligi uchun muhim muammolardan biridir. Ushbu tadqiqotda 2022–2024 yillar davomida O'zbekistonda psixoaktiv moddalar iste'moli tendensiyalari, demografik xususiyatlari, moddalarga bo'lgan afzalliklarning o'zgarishi hamda retsept bo'yicha beriladigan dori vositalarini suiiste'mol qilish holatlari tahlil qilindi.

Metodlar. Rasmiy milliy registrlar va tibbiy statistik hisobotlar asosida retrospektiv kuzatuvchi kohort tadqiqoti o'tkazildi. Uch yil davomida sintetik katinonlar, antikonvulsantlar va boshqa psixoaktiv moddalarni iste'mol qilgan barcha ro'yxatga olingan shaxslar qamrab olindi. Tavsifiy va inferensial statistik usullar, jumladan trend tahlili, χ^2 testi, korrelyatsion tahlil va logistik regressiya qo'llanildi. Natijalar. Ro'yxatga olingan bemorlar soni 2022 yildagi 409 holatdan 2024 yilda 933 holatgacha deyarli ikki baravar oshdi. Erkaklar 89–90% ni tashkil etdi, ayollar soni esa 41 tadan 102 tagacha oshdi. Eng yuqori xavf guruhi 18–34 yoshdagilar bo'lib, ular jami holatlarning qariyb 70% ini tashkil etdi. Sintetik katinonlar orasida α -PVP mefedronni siqib chiqarib yetakchi modda bo'ldi (36 dan 319 holatgacha). Pregabalin eng ko'p suiiste'mol qilinadigan dori vositasiga aylandi (274 holat, 2024 yil). Tropikamid iste'moli barqaror bo'lsa-da, umumiy ulushi kamaydi. Xulosa. O'zbekistonda psixoaktiv moddalar iste'moli tuzilmasi keskin o'zgarib, sintetik katinonlar va retsept dorilarining ulushi oshib bormoqda. α -PVP ustunligi va pregabalin suiiste'molining ortishi qat'iy nazorat choralari, profilaktik dasturlarni va davolash imkoniyatlarini kengaytirishni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sintetik katinonlar, α -PVP, mefedron, pregabalin, psixoaktiv moddalar iste'moli tendensiyalari, O'zbekiston, jamoat salomatligi, retsept dorilarini suiiste'mol qilish, epidemiologiya, qaramlik.

АШУРОВ ЗарифжонКафедра психиатрии и наркологии
Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет, г. Ташкент, Узбекистан**АБДУКАХАРОВА Гулноза**Кафедра психиатрии и наркологии
Ташкентский государственный медицинский университет, г. Ташкент, Узбекистан**НАРАСТАЮЩАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА УПОТРЕБЛЕНИЯ СИНТЕТИЧЕСКИХ КАТИНОНОВ И ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЕНИЯ РЕЦЕПТУРНЫМИ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫМИ ПРЕПАРАТАМИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Рост распространенности синтетических наркотических веществ и психоактивных лекарственных препаратов представляет собой значимую проблему общественного здравоохранения. В исследовании проанализированы тенденции употребления психоактивных веществ в Узбекистане за 2022–2024 годы с учетом демографических характеристик, структуры предпочтений и роста злоупотребления рецептурными препаратами.

Методы. Проведено ретроспективное когортное исследование на основе данных

национальных регистров и медицинской статистики. Используются методы описательной и инференциальной статистики, включая χ^2 , корреляционный анализ и логистическую регрессию.

Результаты. Число случаев увеличилось с 409 (2022) до 933 (2024). Мужчины — 89–90%. Основная группа риска — 18–34 года (~70%). α -PVP стал доминирующим стимулятором (36 → 319 случаев). Прегабалин — ведущий препарат злоупотребления (274 случая). Тропикамид стабилен, но доля снижается.

Выводы. Отмечается трансформация структуры употребления ПАВ с ростом роли синтетических катинов и рецептурных препаратов. Требуется усиление контроля, профилактика и расширение лечения.

Ключевые слова: синтетические катиноны, α -PVP, мефедрон, прегабалин, тенденции употребления, Узбекистан, общественное здравоохранение, злоупотребление рецептурными препаратами, эпидемиология, зависимость.

Introduction

The use of synthetic narcotic substances and psychoactive pharmaceutical drugs has emerged as a growing public health concern worldwide [1,2]. In recent years, many countries, including Uzbekistan, have reported a rising prevalence of synthetic cathinones, prescription drug misuse, and changes in drug consumption patterns. Synthetic cathinones, commonly known as "bath salts," are potent stimulants that mimic the effects of amphetamines and have been linked to severe psychiatric complications [3].

Parallel to the rise of synthetic stimulants, the misuse of prescription medications, particularly anticonvulsants such as pregabalin and gabapentin, has become increasingly common [4,5]. Pregabalin, originally developed for treating epilepsy and neuropathic pain, has anxiolytic and sedative properties, making it an attractive option for recreational use and self-medication. The growing accessibility of these substances—both through illicit drug markets and the diversion of pharmaceuticals—has contributed to an evolving substance use landscape that demands systematic investigation.

Substance Use Trends in Uzbekistan. Although global studies have extensively documented the patterns of synthetic drug and prescription medication misuse, limited research has focused on Uzbekistan and the broader Central Asian region. Given the rapid emergence of new psychoactive substances (NPS) and the increased availability of prescription drugs, understanding local epidemiological trends is crucial for developing effective prevention, treatment, and policy interventions.

Study Objectives. The primary aim of this study is to analyze trends in synthetic cathinone and prescription drug use in Uzbekistan from 2022 to 2024.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This study employs an observational retrospective cohort design to analyze trends and factors influencing the use of synthetic narcotic substances and psychoactive pharmaceutical drugs in Uzbekistan between 2022 and 2024. The research is based on official data concerning registered individuals who consume these substances, sourced from national reports and official databases.

Study Population

This study examines all individuals officially registered as users of synthetic narcotic substances and psychoactive pharmaceutical drugs in Uzbekistan from 2022 to 2024. Data were obtained from national registries and medical statistical reports, ensuring a comprehensive overview of substance use trends during this period.

1. **Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.** The study population consists of all registered users of the specified substances within the designated timeframe.

2. **Sample Characteristics.** To provide a structured understanding of the study population, several key parameters were considered:

Gender distribution: The dataset includes both male and female users, allowing for a comparative analysis of substance use patterns by sex.

Age groups: The population is categorized into distinct age brackets (0–14, 15–17, 18–19, 20–24, 25–29, 30–34, 35–39, 40–64, and 65+ years), facilitating an age-specific evaluation of substance use trends.

Categories of substances consumed: synthetic cathinones (including α -PVP and mephedrone); anticonvulsants (such as pregabalin, gabapentin, and carbamazepine); tropicamide.

3. Population Size and Trends. Over the three-year period analyzed, the number of registered users was 1972.

Data Collection Methods

Data were collected through a retrospective analysis of national medical reports and epidemiological summaries. The following sources were utilized: official statistics and national registries containing annual records of registered users of narcotic and psychoactive substances.

Independent and Dependent Variables

The study assesses independent and dependent variables to identify patterns of substance use and the factors influencing them. Independent variables included the type of psychoactive substance used and demographic characteristics (age, gender)..

The dependent variable was frequency of substance use, trends in substance consumption, age and gender differences in the consumption of various substance groups.

Statistical Data Analysis

A combination of descriptive and inferential statistical methods was employed to analyze the data, ensuring the assessment of normality and adherence to statistical assumptions. The analysis was conducted using SPSS version 29.0.2.0.

Descriptive Statistics

Mean values, medians, standard deviations, and interquartile ranges were calculated for continuous variables. Percentage distributions were reported for categorical variables (gender, age groups, types of substances used).

Data were visually represented using histograms, boxplots, and scatter plots.

Normality Testing.

Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Parametric methods (t-tests, Pearson correlation) were applied when normality assumptions were met. Nonparametric methods (Mann-Whitney U test, Spearman correlation) were used when data deviated from normality.

Comparison of Categorical Data

The Chi-square (χ^2) test was utilized to determine gender-based differences in substance use prevalence. The Kruskal-Wallis test and Mann-Whitney U test were employed to compare substance use across different age groups, particularly in cases where data were not normally distributed.

Trend Analysis

Longitudinal trends in substance use from 2022 to 2024 were evaluated using linear trend analysis. Changes in the number of registered users were examined through linear regression modeling.

Correlation Analysis

Relationships between age, gender, and substance use were assessed through correlation coefficients: Pearson correlation for normally distributed data; Spearman correlation for non-normally distributed data; logistic regression analysis was conducted to explore potential interactions between age, gender, and substance choice.

Statistical Significance Criteria

All statistical tests were performed at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The Bonferroni correction was applied to account for multiple comparisons.

Results

Over the three-year period, the number of identified substance users has nearly doubled, highlighting an escalating public health concern (2022: 409 registered cases; 2023: 630 cases (+54% compared to 2022); 2024: 933 cases (+48% compared to 2023).

The majority of registered users are male, accounting for approximately 89–90% of cases. While women represent only 10–11% of cases, their numbers have increased steadily, from 41 cases in 2022 to 102 in 2024.

Young adults aged 18–34 years are the most at-risk group, comprising nearly 70% of all recorded cases. The 25–34 age group is the most affected, accounting for approximately 50% of users in 2024. The 30–39 age group is expanding, indicating a gradual broadening of the age range associated with substance use.

Trends in Substance Use

The structure of psychoactive substances consumed has changed in 2022–2024. Key results are summarized in Table 1.

THE STRUCTURE OF PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCES CONSUMED

Substance Category	2022	2023	2024
Synthetic Cathinones (Total)	183	315	538
– including α -PVP	36	208	319
– including Mephedrone	133	102	181
Anticonvulsants (Total)	201	286	365
– including Pregabalin	171	213	274
– including Gabapentin	21	20	22
– including Carbamazepine	6	0	7
Tropicamide	25	29	30

Key Findings

- Synthetic cathinone use has surged, with cases tripling between 2022 and 2024. In 2022, mephedrone was the most commonly used synthetic cathinone. By 2023–2024, α -PVP had replaced mephedrone as the dominant synthetic stimulant. In 2024, α -PVP was identified in 319 cases, making it the most widely used synthetic narcotic.

- Pregabalin remains the most commonly misused anticonvulsant, with 274 cases recorded in 2024.

- Gabapentin and carbamazepine play a minor role, with approximately 20 recorded cases annually.

- Tropicamide usage has remained relatively stable, with 25–30 cases per year, although its overall proportion within the dataset has declined.

Correlations and Patterns

The relationship between gender, age and type of substance used is quite clear in the data. The main correlations and patterns observed are:

- Young males (18–34 years) represent the highest-risk demographic.
- Synthetic cathinones are primarily consumed by younger users (18–29 years), while pregabalin is more common among older individuals (30+ years).

- Women are more likely than men to use tropicamide, though female users remain a minority overall.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal a significant increase in the number of registered users of synthetic cathinones, anticonvulsants, in Uzbekistan from 2022 to 2024. The data highlight several concerning trends, including the rapid rise in synthetic cathinone use, shifts in substance preferences. These trends point to an evolving drug consumption landscape that necessitates targeted policy responses and public health interventions.

Rising Prevalence of Synthetic Cathinones

The study demonstrates a threefold increase in synthetic cathinone use over the three-year period, with cases rising from 183 in 2022 to 538 in 2024. While mephedrone was the dominant cathinone in 2022, its prevalence declined in 2023 and 2024, coinciding with a sharp increase in α -PVP use. By 2024, α -PVP had become the most commonly used synthetic stimulant, recorded in 319 cases, compared to 181 cases of mephedrone. This shift is particularly concerning as α -PVP is associated with more severe neuropsychiatric effects, including aggression, paranoia, and prolonged psychotic states. The growing preference for stronger, more addictive synthetic drugs suggests that users may be seeking more potent psychoactive effects, leading to increased health risks and treatment challenges.

Sustained Increase in Anticonvulsant Misuse

The misuse of anticonvulsant medications, particularly pregabalin, has also seen a steady rise. Pregabalin cases increased from 171 in 2022 to 274 in 2024, making it the most frequently misused pharmaceutical in this category. Given pregabalin's anxiolytic and sedative properties, its increasing misuse may be linked to self-medication for anxiety, withdrawal symptoms, or recreational effects. While gabapentin and carbamazepine play a smaller role in substance misuse, the sporadic re-emergence of carbamazepine cases in 2024 warrants further monitoring. Unlike synthetic cathinones, which are typically obtained through illicit markets, pregabalin is a prescription drug, raising concerns about pharmaceutical diversion.

Gender and Age Disparities in Substance Use

A clear gender disparity exists in the study population, with males accounting for nearly 90% of all registered users. Although female users represent a small proportion (10–11%), their numbers have steadily increased from 41 cases in 2022 to 102 in 2024. In terms of age distribution, the highest rates of substance use are concentrated in the 18–34 age group, which accounts for approximately 70% of all cases. However, an expansion in the 30–39 and 40–49 age groups in 2024 suggests a gradual aging of the user demographic. This trend may be indicative of long-term substance dependence, changes in drug availability, or the spread of substance use beyond younger populations.

Conclusions

The findings suggest that Uzbekistan is experiencing a notable rise in substance use, marked by the increasing consumption of synthetic cathinones and the growing misuse of prescription medications. The shift toward more potent substances like α -PVP raises significant concerns for public health and addiction treatment services. Effectively addressing this issue requires a comprehensive approach, incorporating stricter regulatory measures, expanded access to treatment, and well-targeted prevention efforts to reduce the prevalence of synthetic and psychoactive substance use.

REFERENCES | ЧОККИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. N. Nadal-Gratacós, M. D. Pazos, D. Pubill, J. Camarasa, E. Escubedo, X. Berzosa, R. López-Arnau, "Structure-Activity Relationship of Synthetic Cathinones: An Updated Review," *ACS Pharmacol. Transl. Sci.*, vol. 7, no. 9, pp. 2588–2603, 2024. doi: 10.1021/acspstsci.4c00299. PMID: 39296271; PMCID: PMC11406692.
2. S. Chen, W. Zhou, M. Lai, "Synthetic Cathinones: Epidemiology, Toxicity, Potential for Abuse, and Current Public Health Perspective," *Brain Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 334, 2024. doi:10.3390/brainsci14040334. PMID: 38671986.
3. G. Daziani, A. F. Lo Faro, V. Montana, G. Goteri, M. Pesaresi, G. Bambagiotti, E. Montanari, R. Giorgetti, A. Montana, "Synthetic Cathinones and Neurotoxicity Risks: A Systematic Review," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 6230, 2023. doi:10.3390/ijms24076230.
4. M. Perelló, K. Rio-Aige, P. Rius, F. J. Pérez-Cano, M. Rabanal, "Characteristics of Non-Therapeutic Pregabalin Users Detected by a Community Pharmacies Network in a Region of Southern Europe," *J. Clin. Med.*, vol. 13, no. 19, pp. 5942, 2024. doi:10.3390/jcm13195942. PMID: 39408002.

5. G. Z. İspir, M. Danışman, K. S. Katar, “A Hidden Pandemic? Abuse of Gabapentinoids: A Brief Review of Recent Studies,” *Curr. Drug Res. Rev.*, 2023. doi:10.2174/0125899775268780231002064605. PMID: 38031769.

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000